

A compilation and critical evaluation of the literature data on thermal dehydration of hydrated salts

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Abstract : The article provides a detailed compilation of literature data on the thermal dehydration of simple (formed from single cation and anion) hydrated salts consisting of a wide variety of cations and anions or ligands. An attempt has been made to correlate the temperature and apparent activation energy of dehydration with either charge density (z/r) of cation or stability constant ($\log K$) of metal-ligand complex. It is observed that the correlations are complex as they are dependent on the nature of both cation and anion. It is suggested that precise and well-documented data of the dehydration of crystalline hydrated salts are necessary to arrive at meaningful correlation with adequate theoretical basis.

Keywords : Hydrated salts, thermal dehydration, literature data, charge density of cations, stability constants of metal-ligand complexes.

Introduction

Crystalline hydrated salts represent one of the earliest class of compounds whose dehydration under the influence of heat has been used as a model for studying solid state reaction by a large number of investigators. A review of the earlier literature on this topic has been made in 1980 by Brown *et al.*¹, in 1992 by Galwey² and more recently by Kanungo and Mishra³. It has been observed that the thermal stability of a crystalline hydrated salt depends upon the nature of both cation and anion constituting the salt. Despite extensive investigation on this subject no definite conclusions, which could lead to the development of theoretical basis for understanding as well as predicting dehydration behavior, have so far been reached. This is mainly because of the wide variation and lack of sufficient accuracy in the published experimental results. For example, there are instances wherein a hydrated salt has been found to dehydrate in one step or more than one steps at varying temperatures by different workers (see Table 1). One of the main reasons for such variations in the literature data was the lack of uniform or standard procedures adopted by earlier investigators not only in their experiments, but also in reporting the results. This aspect has not been adequately highlighted as

critical reviews of the published results have not been undertaken so far.

An attempt has therefore been made to compile the relevant data on the thermal dehydration of simple hydrated salts comprising different metal ions and ligands and correlate these not only with the charge density of metal ions, but also with the stability of metal-ligand vis-a-vis metal-OH complexes.

Procedure :

Data acquisition : As stated above, hydrated salts selected in this review are simple i.e. consisting of a cation and an anion or ligand. Neither double salts nor hydrated complexes with more than one ligand are considered in this compilation. The anions constitute a wide spectrum of inorganic and organic ligands. Further, dehydroxylation reaction i.e. removal of water from hydroxides, oxyhydroxides, clays etc. are also not included as they constitute distinctly different class of compounds.

The survey has been made mainly from the papers published in the *Thermochimica Acta* and the *Journal of Thermal Analysis*. Survey through *Chemical Abstract* was not helpful as it did not provide all the necessary information required for this work. Therefore, the compilation is not claimed to be exhaustive one. Some earlier

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references have been cited by Berg⁴. The kinetic model codes used are in accordance with the convention followed in the thermal analysis literature. However, the entire compilation comprising more than ten pages could not be reproduced here due to space constraint. Therefore, only those selected hydrated salts whose dehydration data have been used in the correlations attempted in this paper, are presented in Table 1.

There is considerable uncertainty in the thermal dehydration parameters reported by different authors. Variations observed in the salts like $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Li}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been discussed in the previous article³. The situation becomes more complicated when the data reported are incomplete. For example, in some cases in Table 1, the temperature range of dehydration is mentioned, but peak temperature is missing. In such cases we have used mean temperature which may not be true peak temperature. In other cases, heating rate, nature of environment, sample weight etc. have not been clearly stated. Heats of dehydration have been seldom determined; even if determined their units i.e. whether per mole of water or per mole of salt have not been explicitly mentioned. Even in an important review article the author⁵ failed to provide necessary data on the thermal dehydration of hydrated oxalates of different metals. Consequently, though every effort was made to utilize the data obtained under nearly similar condition but it could not be followed always and therefore deviations are bound to occur. Thus, the error range for "mean temperature" is at least ± 10 – 15% and for reported peak temperature the range is ± 5 – 8% . As far as apparent activation energy is concerned, no method can provide a value with precision better than ± 5 – 6% . This can be as high as $\pm 20\%$ if the value is determined from a single TG or DTA or DSC curve using some old, less reliable methods.

The cationic radii data used in the present work are based on the coordination number six. These values are close to those calculated according to the Pauling's method (Ref. 6) and tabulated in many text or reference books^{6–8}. However, minor differences do exist in the compilation by different authors and such differences seldom exceed ± 4 – 5% .

The stability constant values were taken mainly from the compilation by Smith and Martell⁹ and a few from Sillen and Martell¹⁰. Additional information were obtained from the compilation by Turner *et al.*¹¹ (subject to correction for zero ionic strength) and also from Lurie⁸. The uncertainty in the stability constant data varies from com-

plex to complex and even the authors are not explicit on the range of errors. Nevertheless, the error is within ± 5 – 6% and seldom exceeds $\pm 10\%$.

Results and discussion

The thermoanalytical data in Table 1 have been examined from two aspects. First, correlation of thermal stability with the polarizing power of the cations. This parameter is usually called ionic potential or charge density (ϕ) and is represented as follows⁶.

$$\phi = \frac{\text{Charge } (z)}{\text{Radius of the cation } (r)}$$

The effect of the polarizing power of cations on the electron cloud of anion increases as the value of ϕ increases. Consequently, the percent of covalent character of the bond increases and hence bond strength also increases. Using the Born-Landé's derivation^{6,12} of electrostatic attraction between cation and anion in an ionic crystal, Turner *et al.*¹¹ have expressed the polarizing power as $z^2/(r + 0.85)$ where, 0.85 is an empirical correction factor to the Born function z^2/r for salts of 1–1 ionic charges. While there is no difference in the nature of correlations whether the polarizing power is expressed as z/r or z^2/r , the expression of Turner *et al.*¹¹ is irrelevant in the present work, as we are neither dealing with electrostatic energy factor nor with all ionic crystals.

Secondly, in a hydrated salt there are two ligands, namely, the one (L) with which the cation (M) forms the salt and the other is H_2O with which the salt forms hydrate. The stability of the hydrate relative to the salt depends upon the stability ratio of the two ligands. However, there are no data available in the literature for the stability constant of the reaction between M^{n+} and H_2O i.e. hydration of cation. As a result, thermal dehydration parameters have been correlated with the stability constants of metal-ligand interaction. According to spectrochemical series⁶ the strength of the complex formation of a metal ion with either OH or H_2O is almost similar. Indeed, whether OH or H_2O , metal ion would first form covalent bond with oxygen, which, in turn, combine with either one or two hydrogen ions depending upon the strength of covalency of the M–O bond. At the same time metal ion also forms bonds with either O or N or halides etc. of the salt forming ligand. It is assumed that the ratio between the stability constants of M–OH and M–L may represent relative stability of the hydrates. But, how far such an assumption is valid from the point of view of

Table 1. Thermal dehydration characteristics of some selected hydrated salts of various cations and anions

Metal	Hydrated salt (solid)	Melting temp. if occurs	Moles of H ₂ O lost in each step and environment employed	Temp. range of each step of hydration (°C)	Peak temp. (°C) for each step and heating rate (°C/min)	Heat of dehydration (kJ/mol)	Kinetics of dehydration				Order Refs. (n)
							Isothermal method		Non-isothermal method		
							Mechanistic model (code)	App. E (kJ/mol) per sec.	Method/Model C.R. (A2)	App. E (kJ/mol) per sec.	
Barium	Ba ₂ O ₆ .2H ₂ O	N.R.	2 (N ₂ flow)	45-85	70 (5)	-	-	-	158	-	15
	Ba(IO ₃) ₂ .H ₂ O	"	1 (static air)	197-200	198.5 (5)	40.5	-	Diff al	44	4.04	16,17
	BaC ₂ O ₄ .0.5H ₂ O	N.R.	0.5 (air flow)	150-200	-	-	-	-	42.6	-	18
	Ba(CH ₃ COO) ₂ .3H ₂ O melts		3 (dehyd from molten phase)	50-145	125 (5)	79.6	-	-	-	-	19
Cadmium	CdS ₂ O ₆ .4H ₂ O	"	2 (N ₂ flow)	30-66	-	-	-	C-R (reac. order)	118	-	1 20
			2 "	70-135	-	-	-	"	98	-	1.33
Calcium	Cd(HCOO) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	35-78	73 (5)	118.6	R3	88.2	11.19	95.2	0.68 13
	CaS ₂ O ₆ .4H ₂ O	N.R.	4 (N ₂ flow)	35-103	90 (5)	-	-	-	-	105.8	15
	Ca(IO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	Poss'ly melts	5 (static air)	-	110 (5)	-	-	Differential (Am)	115	13.98	m=3 16,17
			1 "	-	160 "	-	-	Differential (F1)	127	13.5	1
Cerium	CaCO ₃ .H ₂ O	No melting	For summary of a large number of data please see Ref. 3								
	Ce ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ .5H ₂ O	"	3 "	57-184	-	-	-	D3	107.1	10.01	21
			1 "	184-264	-	-	-	D4	26.7	-2.99	-
Cesium			1 "	264-329	-	-	-	D4	24	-2.93	-
	Cs ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .H ₂ O	"	1 (N ₂ flow)	35-76	74	-	-	-	107.4	-	22
	CoSO ₄ .6H ₂ O		2 (H ₂ O sat. N ₂ flow)	-	100	-	-	H ₂ O sat. N ₂ flow	96.1	-	23
			3 "	-	-	-	-	-	37.6	-	-
Cobalt			1 "	-	300	-	-	-	62.7	-	-
	Co(IO ₃) ₂ .4H ₂ O	N.R.	4 (air flow)	125-165	150 (5)	51.3	-	Diff al (power law)	86	7.56	1/3 17
	CoS ₂ O ₆ .6H ₂ O	N.R.	2 (N ₂ flow)	56-85	-	-	-	C-R (reac. order)	142	-	1 20
			2 "	86-112	-	-	-	"	260	-	1.33
Copper	Co(CH ₃ COO) ₂ .2H ₂ O	N.R.	2 "	121-225 (with decompn.)	-	-	-	-	64	-	0
	Co(HCCO) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	2H ₂ O	58-104	-	-	-	C-R (reac. order)	115.4	13.79	0.67 24
	CoC ₂ O ₄ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	100-182	159	127.3	R3	112.4	10.4	111.6	0.65 13
	Co(C ₃ O ₄ H ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O	N.R.	2 (N ₂ flow)	130-200	-	-	-	-	157.6	15.73	1 24
Copper	Malonate		2 (N ₂ flow)	140-240	179.4 (5)	95.3	-	Ozawa	62	6.08	25
			2 (air flow)	-	184	-	-	"	125	13.9	-
	CuS ₂ O ₆ .3.5H ₂ O	"	0.5 (N ₂ flow)	35-70	-	-	-	C-R (reac. order)	201	-	2.3 20
Copper			3 (with decompn.)	76-160	-	-	-	"	162	-	2
	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	Melts at 60-63°	2 (N ₂ flow)	63-65	64 (2)	55.6/mol of H ₂ O	-	-	-	-	26
		with mass loss	2 "	81-92	82	55.4	-	-	-	-	-
		1 "	210-230	212	55.9	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table-1 (contd.)

Cu(HCOO) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	69-103	87 (5)	127.7	R3	102.8	12.92	"	103	-	0.61	13
"	"	"	-	84 (10)	-	R3/F1	99/132.6	12.5/17.7	-	-	-	-	27
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·H ₂ O	N.R.	1 (N ₂ flow)	70-125	-	-	-	-	-	"	105.7	11.3	0.67	24
"	"	1 (air flow)	90-180	-	-	-	-	-	"	57.4	8.36	0.2	28
Dysprosium Dy(HCO ₂) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	77-142	135 (5)	105.8	-	-	-	F-C and C-R	111.7 (Av.)	15.72	0.67	14
Erbium Er(HCO ₂) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 "	93-141	124 (5)	131.4	-	-	-	"	120.9 (Av.)	14.12	0.75	14
Er ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₃ ·6H ₂ O	N.R.	3 (air/N ₂ flow)	80-400	90	-	-	-	-	-	42	-	-	29
"	"	1 "	-	150	-	-	-	-	-	45	-	-	-
"	"	2 "	-	380	-	-	-	-	-	105	-	-	-
Holmium HO(HCO ₂) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	81-140	128 (5)	114.2	-	-	-	"	117.3 (Av.)	14.62	0.65	14
Iron(II) FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	N.R.	6 "	60-200	170 (10)	211	-	-	-	-	63 (mean)	-	-	30
"	"	1 "	200-380	350 (*)	50.2	-	-	-	-	70.6 "	-	-	-
FeC ₂ O ₄ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 (N ₂ flow)	120-185	-	-	-	-	-	C-R (reac.order)	106.2	9.52	-	24
"	"	2 (air/Ar flow)	140-190	180 (5)	-	-	-	-	-	86	-	-	31
Fe(HCO ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 "	97-157	142 (5)	123.7	R3	104.1	10.05	"	108.3	-	0.69	13
Fe ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ ·7H ₂ O	"	vacuum	260-317	297	-	-	219	-	-	-	-	-	32
Lanthanum La ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₃ ·10H ₂ O	"	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Last step of dehydration	"	2 (air flow)	-	360 (5)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lithium Li ₂ SO ₄ ·H ₂ O	"	1 (N ₂ flow)	89-145	133 (5)	-	-	-	-	-	108	-	-	33
"	"	2 (static air)	54-74	70 (5)	-	-	-	-	-	93	-	-	34
Lead Pb(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 (N ₂ flow)	23-60	-	-	-	-	-	-	145	-	-	35
Lutetium Lu(HCO ₂) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	89-132	117 (5)	146.9	-	-	-	F-C and C-R	136.4	15.82	0.71	14
Magnesium MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	"	0.5 "	275-310	320 (5)	-	-	-	-	-	(Av.)	(Av.)	-	36
Last step of dehydration	"	2 (static air)	34-54	- (5)	-	-	-	-	-	145	-	-	35
Mg ₂ O ₆ ·7H ₂ O	N.R.	2 "	74-106	-	-	-	-	-	-	221	-	-	-
"	"	3 "	133-218	-	-	-	-	-	-	140	-	-	-
Mg(IO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	"	4 (static air)	160-175	165 (5)	-	-	-	-	R3	79	7.03	-	17
MgC ₂ O ₄ ·2H ₂ O	"	1 (N ₂ flow)	175-223	-	-	-	-	-	"	91.3	7.67	m=2.36	37
"	"	1 "	130-250	-	-	-	-	-	"	117	10.7	m=2	-
"	"	2 (N ₂ flow)	45-125	-	-	-	-	-	"	211.9	21.81	1	24
Mg(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	"	4 "	108-185	169 (5)	-	-	-	-	-	152.1	20.62	2	24
Mg(HCOO) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	50-300	233-238 (10)	166.3	R3	105.7	10.17	C-R (reac.order)	109.6	-	0.64	13
Mg(C ₃ O ₄ H ₂) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	"	3 "	-	-	-	-	-	-	C-R	118.8	10	0.54	38
(Malonate)	"	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

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Table-1 (contd.)

Manganese	MnSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	N.O.	2 (static air)	120-190	172 (5)	-	-	-	-	F1	60.6	39
			2 "	280-380	340 "	-	-	-	-	F1	20.2	
	Mn(HCOO) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	2 "	84-140	132 (5)	120.5/116	R3	104.5	12.86	C-R (reac.order)	106.6	13
	MnC ₂ O ₄ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (Ar flow)	116-140	134 (10)	-	-	-	-	"	280	16.14
	"	"	"	100-164	131 (10)	-	-	73	6.67	Differ'nl method	86	41
Nickel	NiSO ₄ .6H ₂ O	Last step of 1 (static air) crystallized at 40° dehydration	2 (static air)	330-400	358 (20)	-	-	-	-	-	-	39
	Ni(S ₂ O ₆).6H ₂ O	N.R.	2 (N ₂ flow)	30-65	-	-	-	-	-	C-R (reac.order)	108	1
			2 "	66-107	-	-	-	-	-	"	185	1.33
			2 (with decom-position)	115-220	-	-	-	-	-	"	76	-
	Ni(IO ₃) ₂ .4H ₂ O	N.R.	2 (static air)	-	120 (5)	-	-	-	-	Differential (F1)	76	7.96
			2 "	-	230 "	-	-	-	-	" (D4)	118	9.34
	Ni(HCOO) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	2 "	114-203	177 (5)	127.7	R3	110.8	10.08	C-R (reac.order)	117.3	0.76
	NiC ₂ O ₄ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (N ₂ flow)	135-260	-	-	-	-	-	"	252.5	2
	NiC ₃ O ₄ H ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (air/N ₂ flow)	185-258	231/233 (5)	121.4	-	-	-	"	154	42
	(Malonate)									/105	11.3	
Sodium	CH ₃ COONa.3H ₂ O	Melts at 70°3	(N ₂ flow)	75-140	130 (5)	39.56	-	-	-	C-R and Zsako	3.74	5.25
	Na ₂ (S ₂ O ₆).2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	32-58	45 "	-	-	-	-	"	149	35
Strontium	Sr(IO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	Poss'ly melts	5 "	90-100	95 (5)	-	-	-	Zero order	81	10.07	16,17
			1 "	170-188	174 "	-	-	-	-	Power law	87	7.86
	Sr(IO ₃) ₂ .H ₂ O	"	1 "	-	170 "	46	-	-	-	R3	120	13.24
Thulium	Tm(HCO ₂) ₃ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	80-134	118 (5)	141.8	-	-	-	F-C and R-S (order)	136.6	14.72
Yttrium	Y(HCO ₂) ₃ .2H ₂ O	"	2 "	80-140	121 (5)	115	-	-	-	F-C and R-S (order)	118	17.04
	Y ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₃ .2H ₂ O	"	1 (N ₂ flow)	320-357	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Last step of dehydration											
Ytterbium	Yb(HCO ₂) ₃ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	81-145	120 (5)	145.6	-	-	-	F-C and R-S (order)	139.9	17.2
Zinc	Zn(IO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O	N.R.	2 "	-	140 (5)	-	-	-	-	Diffi' al (power law)	123	12.07
	Zn(HCOO) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	2 "	70-112	110 (5)	123.3	R3	100.3	11.25	"	102.6	0.68
	"	"	2 (N ₂ flow)	85-120	-	-	-	-	-	"	160.1	19.67
	Zn(C ₂ H ₃ O ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	2 (static air)	60-78 (Isothermal mass loss exp'us)	-	-	R3	101.3	11.74	"	-	-
	(Acetate)	"	2 "	50-150	-	-	-	-	-	"	45	8.08
Zirconium	Zr(SO ₄) ₂ .5H ₂ O	N.O.										28
	Last step of dehydration in TG											
	Last step of dehydration in DSC											
			1 (N ₂ flow)	250-305	330 (5)	-	-	-	-			45
												28

40/mol of monohydrate

Abbreviations used : N.O. Not reported; N.O. Not observed; C-R Coates and Redfern; M-T MacCallum and Tanner; O-F-W Ozawa, Flynn and Wall; H-M Horowitz and Metzger; F-C Freeman and Carroll; R-S Reich and Stivala; Z-Z Zsako and Zsako. For details of these methods please see either Ref. 1 or a review article by the author in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 315-328.

field stabilization energy (cfse) helps to maintain predominantly covalent character even for weak complexes.

Fig. 2 depicts the plots of apparent activation energy (E_a) of dehydration of the salts of different ligands vs charge density of metals. The nature of the plots appears to be opposite to that in Fig. 1, despite paucity of data. The increasing trend of dehydration temperature in Fig. 1 becomes a decreasing trend of E_a and vice versa in Fig. 2. Activation energy is the manifestation of temperature coefficient of the rate of reaction and therefore represents kinetic stability of the hydrated salts. It indicates whether

Fig. 2. Variation of apparent activation energy (E_a) of the thermal dehydration of hydrated salts of some selected ligands with z/r of metal ions.

the dehydration reaction proceeds fast enough (labile) or relatively slow with respect to rise in temperature (inert). On the other hand, temperature of dehydration is related to the enthalpy of reaction which is a thermodynamic quantity determined from stability constants under equilibrium condition. In fact, there is no correlation between thermodynamic and kinetic constants. In other words, "labile" complexes are not necessarily thermodynamically unstable and "inert" complexes are not thermodynamically

stable. Therefore, larger the value of E_a the lower will be the lability of the compound, which means that hydrates with higher E_a value for dehydration will react slowly.

Dehydration of formates :

Masuda and Shishido¹³ and Masuda¹⁴ have carried out detailed investigation on the thermal dehydration of metal formate dihydrates. All these salts dehydrate in single step by losing two moles of H_2O at respective well defined peak temperatures. The authors have also reported apparent activation energy (E_a) and heat of dehydration (ΔH_{deh}) for each dehydration reaction. Fig. 3 shows that while the peak temperature for dehydration of certain metals of 4f series (Dy-Lu) tend to decrease with increase in charge density, the results are rather irregular for Cd, Mg and some transition metals. While Zn and Cu show decrease in peak temperature, Fe^{II}, Co and Ni show increasing trend with respect to Mn. The two different behaviors within the same series is difficult to explain except that the effect of cfse which is higher for Fe^{II}, Co and Ni is possibly influencing the thermal stability of the hydrates considerably.

Fig. 3. Variation of peak temperature, E_a and heat of dehydration (ΔH_{deh}) of the thermal dehydration of hydrated formates with z/r of cations.

The variation of both E_a and ΔH_{deh} with ϕ in the case of metal formates of 4f series is closely similar i.e. show increase slowly from Dy to Ho followed by sharp in-

crease to Yb, though Lu show minor decrease in the E_a value. This behavior is almost opposite to the decrease in peak temperature with increase in ϕ . In contrast, E_a values for the dehydration of Cd, Mg and transition metal formates show variation similar to peak temperature with respect to ϕ . We are again unable to provide adequate explanation for this deviation from Fig. 2. However, it may be noted that E_a values are very close to the corresponding ΔH_{deh} values. Possibly, the change in internal energy between initial (reactant) and final state (anhydrous salt) tends to be equal to the difference between initial and transition states. Interestingly, ΔH_{deh} values for the dehydration of these metal formates exhibit increasing trend and lie on a single straight line.

Effect of anion or ligand on thermal stability of hydrates :

As stated earlier in this paper, the stability of a complex increases with increase in the covalent character of the metal-ligand bond. But, how far the stability of a metal-ligand complex would influence the stability of its hydrated state containing H_2O as an additional ligand is

not known, as the stability constant value of $\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex is not available in the literature. It is however assumed that stability of a metal-L complex is directly related to the stability of its corresponding hydrated variety. In other words, thermal stability of both anhydrous and hydrated salts are interrelated as long as both the ligands are bonded to the metal ion by similar bonds. Deviations will, however occur, if $\text{M}-\text{L}$ bond is predominantly ionic in nature as the $\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ bond in an hydrated salt is always coordinate in nature.

To examine the above hypothesis several hydrated salts of Fe^{II} and Mn^{II} have been selected from literature. In this selection, inorganic ligands or anions such as, Cl^- , ClO_4^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} etc. have been avoided, because these anions tend to form predominantly ionic bond with many metals. While the ligands of Fe^{II} salts are of assorted type (Table 2), those constituting Mn salts are dicarboxylic acids of homologous series (Table 3). The stability constants of all the neutral complexes are available in the literature⁹. Fig. 4 shows that there is an excellent correlation between dehydration temperature and stability cons-

Table 2. Stability constants of Fe^{II} complexes (neutral) with some selected ligands and dehydration temperatures of their crystalline hydrates

Sl. no.	Ligand (L)	$\log K_{\text{FeL}}$	$\log (K_{\text{FeOH}}/K_{\text{FeL}})^a$	Hydrated salt	Moles of H_2O lost on dehydration	Peak temp. for dehydration ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Refs.
1.	$\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (Oxalate)	4.40	+0.65	$\text{FeC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-\text{2H}_2\text{O}$	180	31
2.	$\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (Malonate)	3.00	2.03	$\text{FeC}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-\text{2H}_2\text{O}$	200	(i)
3.	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (Succinate)	1.40	3.63	$\text{FeC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-\text{2H}_2\text{O}$	94	(ii)
4.	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5^{2-}$ (Malate)	2.60	2.43	$\text{FeC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-\text{2H}_2\text{O}$	137	(iii)
5.	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_2^{2-}$ (Fumerate)	1.03	4.00	$\text{FeC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-\text{0.5H}_2\text{O}$	102	(iv)
6.	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$ (Tartrate)	2.20	2.85	$\text{FeC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-\text{0.5H}_2\text{O}$ $-\text{2H}_2\text{O}$	120	(v)
7.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7^{3-}$ (Citrate)	3.05	1.98	$\text{Fe}_3(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7)_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-\text{0.5H}_2\text{O}$ $-\text{2H}_2\text{O}$	90 190	(vi)

^a $\log K_{\text{FeOH}} = 5.03$.

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Table 3. Stability constants of Mn^{II} complexes with some homologous dicarboxylates and thermal dehydration parameters of their crystalline hydrates^a

Sl. no.	Ligand (L)	log K_{MnL}	log (K_{MnOH}/K_{MnL}) ^b	Hydrated salt	Moles of H ₂ O lost	Peak temp. for dehydration (°C)	E_a for dehydrn. (kJ/mol)
1.	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ (Oxalate)	3.80	-0.10	MnC ₂ O ₄ ·2H ₂ O	-2H ₂ O	135	280
2.	C ₃ H ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ (Malonate)	3.20	0.50	MnC ₃ H ₂ O ₄ ·2H ₂ O	-2H ₂ O	184	136.3
3.	C ₄ H ₄ O ₄ ²⁻ (Succinate)	2.25	1.45	MnC ₄ H ₄ O ₄ ·4H ₂ O	-4H ₂ O	111	148
4.	C ₅ H ₆ O ₄ ²⁻ (Glutarate)	1.13	2.57	MnC ₅ H ₆ O ₄ ·4H ₂ O	-4H ₂ O	106	122.5
5.	C ₆ H ₈ O ₄ ²⁻ (Adipate)	2.00	1.70	MnC ₆ H ₈ O ₄ ·H ₂ O	-H ₂ O	191	189.3
6.	C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₄ ²⁻ (Pimelate)	1.30	2.40	MnC ₇ H ₁₀ O ₄ ·H ₂ O	-H ₂ O	108	121
7.	C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ ²⁻ (Azelaate)	1.03	2.67	MnC ₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ ·H ₂ O	-H ₂ O	81	91
8.	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ ²⁻ (Sebacate)	1.00	2.70	MnC ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ ·H ₂ O	-H ₂ O	98	110
9.	C ₄ H ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ (Maleate)	1.68	2.02	MnC ₄ H ₂ O ₄ ·4H ₂ O	-4H ₂ O	108	111

^aRef. 40. ^blog K_{MnOH} = 3.70.

Fig. 4. Correlation between peak temperature/app. activation energy (E_a) values for thermal dehydration of some selected hydrated salts of iron(II) and manganese(II) with organic ligands and the corresponding stability constants of M-L complexes. Superscripts denote serial numbers in Tables 2 and 3.

tants of the selected Fe^{II} salts. However, for the hydrated salts of Mn^{II}, no such clear cut correlation can be ob-

served between dehydration temperature and the corresponding stability constants of neutral complexes. On the other hand, some correlation between apparent activation energy of dehydration and stability constant can be noted in Fig. 4 *albeit*, in the form of two different straight lines.

It may also be noted that as the size of the ligand increases in the homologous series, stability constant decreases and so also the corresponding temperature of dehydration and E_a value of the process. This suggests that both ligand (L) and H₂O occur within the same sphere of coordination with the metal ion. If, for the sake of argument, the difference between log K_{MOH} and log K_{ML} is taken as measure of the relative stability of the hydrated salt, an opposite behavior can be noted with the dehydration data in Tables 2 and 3.

The above analysis of the literature data on thermal analysis of hydrated salts has not been able to address adequately the role of salt forming ligand on the dehydration process. Perhaps, it needs in-depth studies of the structure of complexes and Pauling's valence bond principle. Work in this direction is being pursued.

Conclusions :

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above analysis of the literature data on thermal dehydration of hydrated salts.

- (i) Though extensive investigation has been carried out on the thermal dehydration of hydrated salts, many of the data are of limited use because of the lack of uniformity in experimental procedure, presentation of data and more importantly, lack of agreement in results among different workers.
- (ii) It is believed that the physico-chemical principles which govern the formation and stability of chemical compounds should also be applicable to the thermal dehydration of hydrated salts. To establish this, it is necessary to have reasonable precision and agreement on experimental results among different workers.
- (iii) Thermal stability of hydrated salts depends upon the nature of both cation and anion. Normally, cation of high charge density or ionic potential (z/r) tend to form stronger covalent bond. However, some cation of high z/r ratio tend to form electrostatic bond with those anions whose electron clouds are strongly polarized and therefore tend to deviate from the above rule, even though their bonding with H_2O remains primarily coordinate in nature.
- (iv) Thermal dehydration parameters of hydrated salts are, in general, related to the stability constant of metal-ligand complex ($\log K_{ML}$) or inversely to the "relative stability ratio" i.e. $\log (K_{MOH}/K_{ML})$.

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